

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1920	Richard N. Frye	1940	1946	1990		American scholar of Iranian and Central Asian Studies, and Aga Khan Professor Emeritus of Iranian Studies at Harvard University	1920-2014
1920	Fred Lukoff	1942	1954	1989		American linguist (Korean language, phonology), the first president of the International Association for Korean Language Education (IAKLE)	1920-2000
1920	Linda Dégh	1942	1942	1982	w	Hungarian-American folklorist and professor of Folklore & Ethnomusicology	1920-2014
1920	Alicia Dussán de Reichel	1942	1942	2008	w	Colombian educator, who was one of the first students of ethnology in the country	
1920	Evelyn Byrd Harrison	1943	1952	2006	w	American classical scholar and archaeologist	1920-2012
1920	Edward Ullendorff	1945	1952	1982		British linguist and historian	1920-2011
1920	Branko Fučić	1946	1964	1990		Croatian art historian, archeologist and paleographer	1920-1999
1920	Daniel Vidart	1946		1991		Uruguayan anthropologist, writer, historian, and essayist	1920-2019
1920	Jean Starobinski	1946	1958	1985		Swiss literary critic	1920-2019
1920	Victor H. Yngve	1947	1953	1989		American computational linguist (natural language processing)	1920-2012
1920	Ehsan Yarshater	1947	1947	2016		Iranian historian and linguist who specialized in Iranology	1920-2018
1920	Hans Bielenstein	1947	1952	1990		Swedish sinologist and Dean Lung Professor Emeritus	1920-2015
1920	Laurence Thompson	1947	1954	1976		American sinologist, classical violinist and professor emeritus of East Asian languages and cultures	1920-2002
1920	Georges Balandier	1947	1955	1985		French sociologist, anthropologist and ethnologist noted for his research in Sub-Saharan Africa	1920-2016
1920	Edgar Charles Polomé	1948	1949	1997		Belgian professor of comparative religions and languages	1920-2000
1920	Elena Catena	1948		1985	w	Spanish philologist, editor and feminist	1920-2012
1920	Alexander Norman Jeffares	1948		1985		Irish literary scholar	1920-2005
1920	Albert S. Gérard	1948	1955	1996		Belgian scholar of comparative literature, specializing in African literature	1920-1996

1920 Donald Russell	1948	1948	1988	British classicist and academic	1920-2020
1920 Louis Bazin	1949		1990	French Orientalist	1920-2011
1920 Aidan Southall	1949	1952	1990	British cultural anthropologist recognised for his fieldwork in urban settings in post-war Africa	1920-2009
1920 Eric Heaton	1949		1991	British Old Testament scholar and a former Dean of Christ Church	1920-1996
1920 giuliana povoledo	1950		2002 w	French researcher in Music And Theatre	1920-2013
1920 John Chadwick	1950	No	1984	British linguist and classical scholar, decipherment of Linear B	1920-1998
1920 Randolph Quirk	1950	1951	1989	British linguist and life peer (parlament)	1920-2017
1920 Melford Spiro	1950	1950	1990	American cultural anthropologist (religion and psychological anthropology)	1920-2014
1920 Ernestine Friedl	1950	1950	1995 w	American anthropologist, author, and professor	1920-2015
1920 Ahmad Hassan Dani	1950	No	1980	Pakistani archaeologist, historian, and linguist	1920-2009
1920 George Spindler	1950	1952	2006	American leading figure in 20th-century anthropology and the founder of the anthropology of education	1920-2014
1920 Eric P. Hamp	1951	1954	1991	American linguist (Indo-European linguistics)	1920-2019
1920 Paul Bohannan	1951	1951	1987	American cultural anthropologist (Tiv people of Nigeria, spheres of exchange and divorce in the United States)	1920-2007
1920 Wolfgang Preisendanz	1951	1951	1988	German philologist and literary critic (humor especialy)	1920-2007
1920 Mary Boyce	1951	1952	1982 w	British scholar of Iranian languages, and an authority on Zoroastrianism	1920-2006
1920 Zhu Dexi	1951	No	1992	Chinese linguist, grammarian, and educator	1920-1992
1920 Peter Edgar Corbett	1951		1983	British art historian and classical scholar	1920-1992
1920 Victor Turner	1952	1955	1983	British cultural anthropologist (symbols, rituals, and rites of passage)	1920-1983
1920 Zoe Dumitrescu Buşulenga	1952	1970	1997	Romanian comparatist and essayist, ' Mother Benedicta ' (2000-2006)	1920-2006
1920 Robert L. Chapman	1952		1986	American professor of English literature who edited several dictionaries and thesauri	1920-2002
1920 Raoul Naroll	1953	1953	1985	Canadian-American anthropologist (the methodology of cross-cultural studies)	1920-1985
1920 H. W. F. Saggs	1953	1953	1983	British classicist and orientalist	1920-2005
1920 Gerhard Doerfer	1954	1954	1988	German Turkologist, Altaist, and philologist (Turkic languages)	1920-2003

1920	Shaban Demiraj	1954		1990	Albanian Linguist, Albanologist	1920-2014
1920	Aleksander Jackowski	1954		1984	Polish cultural anthropologist, ethnographer, art critic	1920-2017
1920	Margherita Guarducci	1955		1985 w	French ethnologist who specialises on African people, and had worked extensively on the Fulani of Niger, Cameroon, Guinea, Senegal	1920-2015
1920	Walter B. Miller	1955	1960	1980	American anthropologist and was known for his study and publications on youth gangs	1920-2004
1920	Fanny de Sivers	1956		1986	Estonian linguist, literature researcher and essayist	1920-2011
1920	Tadao Umesao	1956	1961	1993	Japanese anthropologist	1920-2010
1920	Gordon Frederick Arnold	1957	No	1982	British linguist	1920-1999
1920	Edward Stankiewicz	1958	1971	1991	Polish-American the B. E. Bensinger Professor of Slavic Languages and Literatures	1920-2013
1920	Bodo Spranz	1958	1958	1984	German researcher of preclassic meso-American history and director of the ethnological museum in Freiburg	1920-2007
1920	Kenneth Dover	1958		2005	British distinguished Classical scholar and academic	1920-2010
1920	Georges Jean	1959		1981	French poet and essayist specializing in the fields of linguistics, semiology and children's literature	1920-2011
1920	Jean Dubois	1960	1962	1986	French 20th-century linguist, grammarian and lexicographer	1920-2015
1920	Mark Krasniqi	1960	1960	1981	Kosovo Albanian ethnographer, publicist, writer, and translator	1920-2015
1920	Harriet Cornelia Mills	1963	1963	1990	American scholar and professor of Chinese language and literature	1920-2016
1920	Joseph Hellegouarc'h	1963	1963	1986	French professor of Latin language and literature	1920-2004
1920	John V. Luce	1968		2005	Irish classicist, former professor and emeritus Fellow of Classics at Trinity College Dublin	1920-2011
1921	Eric Bertrand Ceadel	1940		1979	British japanologist and university administrator	1921-1979
1921	Eugenio Coşeriu	1944	1944	1993	Romanian linguist who specialized in Romance languages at the University of Tübingen	1921-2002
1921	Charles A. Ferguson	1945	1945	1986	American linguist (co-founder of sociolinguistics and is best known for his work on diglossia)	1921-1998
1921	Geoffrey Kirk	1945	1945	1982	British English classicist known for his writings on Ancient Greek literature and mythology	1921-2003

1921	Marija Gimbutas	1946	1946	1987 w	Lithuanian-American archaeologist and anthropologist known for her research into the Neolithic and Bronze Age cultures of "Old Europe" and for her Kurgan hypothesis, which located the Proto-Indo-European homeland in the Pontic Steppe	1921-1994
1921	Stanislav Segert	1947	1947	1990	Czech prominent scholar of Semitic languages and one of the foremost authorities on North-West Semitic languages	1921-2005
1921	Godfrey Lienhardt	1947	1947	1988	British anthropologist	1921-1993
1921	Jacob W. Gruber	1947		1982	American anthropologist, archaeologist, historian of science and educator	1921-2019
1921	A. J. Aitken	1948	No	1986	British (Scottish) lexicographer and leading scholar of the Scots language	1921-1998
1921	Elliott D. Canonge	1948	No	1971	American linguist (Comanche, Inuit)	1921-1971
1921	Virginia Gutiérrez de Pineda	1948	1962	1992 w	Colombian anthropologist who pioneered work on Colombian family and medical anthropology	1921-1999
1921	C. H. van Schooneveld	1949	1949	1987	Dutch linguist (Slavic)	1921-2003
1921	Carl Orkland	1949	1949	1979	Norwegian philologist	1921-1994
1921	Simin Daneshvar	1949	1949	1980 w	Iranian academic, novelist, fiction writer and translator, largely regarded as the first major Iranian woman novelist	1921-2012
1921	Uray Géza	1949		1984	Hungarian tibetologist	1921-1991
1921	Cyril Belshaw	1949	1949	1987	New Zealand-Canadian Anthropologist	1921-2018
1921	Mary Douglas	1950	1953	1978 w	British anthropologist (human culture and symbolism, social anthropology)	1921-2007
1921	AHJ Prins	1950	1953	1984	Dutch Africanist and maritime anthropologist	1921-2000
1921	William L. Moran	1950	1950	1990	American Assyriologist	1921-2000
1921	Heinrich Schmid	1950	1962	1983	Swiss linguist and "father" of the Rhaeto-Romance Dachsprachen ("umbrella languages") Rumantsch Grischun and Ladin Dolomitan	1921-1999
1921	Catharine McClellan	1950	1950	1983 w	American cultural anthropologist who is known for her documentation of the oral history and storytelling typical of Athabascan speaking, Tlingit and Tagish peoples of the Yukon Territory	1921-2009

1921	Ricardo Alegría	1950	1954	1992	Puerto Rican scholar, cultural anthropologist, " father of modern Puerto Rican archaeology "	1921-2011
1921	Emir Rodríguez Monegal	1950	1956	1982	Uruguayan scholar, literary critic, and editor of Latin American literature	1921-1985
1921	Frank Moore Cross	1950	1950	1992	American the Hancock Professor of Hebrew and Other Oriental Languages Emeritus at Harvard University	1921-2012
1921	Roland Frye	1951		1983	American English literature scholar and theologian	1921-2005
1921	Donald Shively	1951	1951	1992	American academic, historian, Japanologist, author and professor emeritus of East Asian Languages and Cultures	1921-2005
1921	A. H. J. Prins	1951	1953	1984	Dutch Africanist and maritime anthropologist	1921-2000
1921	Peter Lawrence	1951	1951	1986	British-Australian anthropologist and pioneer in the study of Melanesian religions	1921-1987
1921	M. G. Smith	1951	1951	1986	Jamaican social anthropologist and poet of international repute	1921-1993
1921	R. H. Robins	1951	1968	1986	British linguist	1921-2000
1921	John C. McLaughlin	1952	1960	1987	American philologist	1921-2013
1921	John Gombojab Hangin	1952	1970	1989	Mongolian scholar of Mongolian studies	1921-1989
1921	William Diver	1953	1953	1989	American linguist (comparative Indo-European linguistics)	1921-1995
1921	John Francis Marchment Middleton	1953	1953	1991	British professor of anthropology in the United States, specializing in Africa	1921-2009
1921	Georges Condominas	1953	No	1987	French cultural anthropologist, who known for his field studies of the Mnong people of Vietnam	1921-2011
1921	George W. Grace	1954	1958	1991	American emeritus professor of linguistics at the University of Hawai'i.	1921-2015
1921	John Burton-Page	1954		1982	British orientalist, Lecturer in the Art and Architecture of India at the School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS)	1921-2005
1921	Alex Wayman	1955	1959	1991	American Tibetologist and Indologist and worked as a professor of Sanskrit	1921-2004
1921	Edith Turner	1955	No	2015 w	British-American anthropologist, poet, and post-secondary educator	1921-2016
1921	René Gsell	1956		1986	French linguist and phonetician	1921-2000
1921	James Kinnier Wilson	1956	No	1989	British Assyriologist	

1921	Daniel J. Crowley	1956	1956	1992	American art historian and cultural anthropologist who focused on the cultural expressions of Sub-Saharan Africa and the Caribbean, with particular focus on the interconnectedness of carnivals, festivals, the arts and folklore	1921-1998
1921	Zeno Vendler	1957	1959	1989	American philosopher of language, event structure	1921-2004
1921	Eric Grinstead	1957	1973	1986	New Zealand sinologist and Tangutologist, who was best known for his analysis of the Tangut script	1921-2008
1921	William Shipley	1958	1964	1991	American linguist and speaker of the Maidu language	1921-2011
1921	Ainslie Embree	1960	1960	1991	Canadian Indologist and historian	1921-2017
1921	Esther Hermitte	1961	1964	1979 w	Argentinean social anthropologist	1921-1990
1921	Maximiliano García Cordero	1961	1964	1991	Spanish professor of religion at the Pontifical University of Salamanca	1921-2012
1921	Jean Duvignaud	1965	1972	1991	French novelist, sociologist and anthropologist	1921-2007
1921	Zdzisław Żygulski	1968		2015	Polish art historian and professor of the Academy of Fine Arts in Kraków	1921-2015
1921	Maurice Sznycer	1972		1981	French historian, philologist, archaeologist, epigrapher and specialist of the Semitic world	
1922	Michael Ventris	1940	1954	1956	British architect, classicist and philologist-genius (deciphered Linear B, the ancient Mycenaean Greek script)	1922-1956
1922	Annemarie Schimmel	1941	1941	1992 w	German influential Orientalist and scholar who wrote extensively on Islam and Sufism	1922-2003
1922	Stanley Marion Garn	1942	1948	1992	American human biologist and educator, Professor of Anthropology at the College for Literature, Science and Arts	1922-2007
1922	Stephen Wurm	1944	1944	1987	Hungarian-Australian linguist	1922-2001
1922	Marie Reay	1945	1957	1988 w	Australian anthropologist, known particularly for work in the New Guinea Highlands	1922-2004
1922	Hans Reiss	1945	1945	2009	German-British professor of German	1922-2020
1922	Eleanor Burke Leacock	1946	1952	1987 w	American anthropologist and social theorist (study of egalitarian societies, the evolution of the status of women in society, marxism, and the feminist movement)	1922-1987

1922	Francisco Rodríguez Adrados	1946	1946	1988	Spanish Hellenist, linguist and translator	
1922	Edmund Snow Carpenter	1947	1950	1999	American anthropologist (tribal art and visual media)	1922-2011
1922	Anne Chapman	1947	1958	1987 w	American Franco-American ethnologist that focused on the people of Mesoamerica	1922-2010
1922	Ilse Lehiste	1948	1948	1987 w	Estonian-American linguist (phonetics)	1922-2010
1922	Frederick W. Mote	1948	1954	1987	American Sinologist and a professor of History	1922-2005
1922	Suzanna W. Miles	1948	1955	1966 w	American ethnohistorian, anthropologist and archaeologist	1922-1966
1922	Frank R. Palmer	1949	No	1987	British linguist	1922-2019
1922	Nelly Naumann	1949	1949	1993 w	German scholar of Japanese studies (Japanese mythology and folklore and Shinto)	1922-2000
1922	Sidney Mintz	1949	1951	1997	American anthropologist (studies of the Caribbean, creolization, and the anthropology of food)	1922-2015
1922	Walter Höllerer	1949	1949	1988	German writer, literary critic and a literature graduate	1922-2003
1922	William Alfred	1949	1954	1991	American playwright, poet, and professor of English literature	1922-1999
1922	Donald Keene	1949	1949	2011	American-Japanese scholar, historian, teacher, writer and translator of Japanese literature	1922-2019
1922	Laura Bohannon	1949	1951	1990 w	American cultural anthropologist	1922-2002
1922	Gerd Koch	1949	1949	1985	German cultural anthropologist best known for his studies on the material culture of Kiribati, Tuvalu and the Santa Cruz Islands in the Pacific	1922-2005
1922	Leslie Bodi	1949	1949	1987	Hungarian-Australian the foundation Professor of German	1922-2015
1922	Egil Pettersen	1950	1950	1989	Norwegian philologist	1922-2010
1922	Zeynep Korkmaz	1950	1950	1990 w	Turkish scholar and dialectologist	
1922	Marius Jansen	1950	1950	1992	Dutch-American academic, historian, and Emeritus Professor of Japanese History	1922-2000
1922	Robert E. Longacre	1951	1955	2001	American linguist and missionary	1922-2014
1922	Stanley Diamond	1951	1951	1991	American poet and anthropologist	1922-1991
1922	Mitchell Dahood	1951	1951	1982	American Jesuit Hebraist and Bible scholar	1922-1982
1922	Max Mangold	1951	1956	1988	Swiss-German linguist and phonetician	1922-2015
1922	Amy Marie Charles	1951	1951	1984	American professor of English literature	1922-1985

1922	Marshall Hodgson	1951	1951	1968	American Islamic studies academic and a world historian	1922-1968
1922	Edwin G. Pulleyblank	1951	1951	1987	Canadian sinologist and professor	1922-2013
1922	Sidney Mintz	1951	1951	1997	American anthropologist best known for his studies of the Caribbean, creolization, and the anthropology of food	1922-2015
1922	George Alphonse De Vos	1951	1951	1991	American professor emeritus of anthropology	1922-2010
1922	Hans-Erich Keller	1952	1952	1994	Swiss professor of French language (Occitan and medieval French literature, and the history of French, Occitan, and Italian, as well as Romance linguistics)	1922-1999
1922	Yuri Knorozov	1952	1955	1999	Russian linguist, epigrapher and ethnographer (decipherment of the Maya script)	1922-1999
1922	Andrzej Zajaczkowski	1952		1994	Polish sociologist, cultural anthropologist, and Africanist	1922-1994
1922	Harald Reiche	1952	1955	1991	German-American classical scholar, specializing in an archaeoastronomical interpretation of Greek mythology	1922-1994
1922	Rudolf Baehr	1952	1952	1990	German Romanist	1922-2010
1922	Robert B. Lees	1953		1996	American linguist	1922-1996
1922	John William Ward	1953		1979	American Professor of History and American Studies, the fourteenth President of Amherst College	1922-1985
1922	John Joseph Gumperz	1954	1954	1991	American sociolinguist, discourse analysis, linguistic anthropology, and urban anthropology	1922-2013
1922	Androkli Kostallari	1954		1992	Albanian linguist, lexicologist and academic	1922-1992
1922	Maja Bošković-Stulli	1954	1961	1979 w	Croatian slavist and folklorist, literary historian, writer, publisher and an academic (Croatian oral literature)	1922-2012
1922	Eyvind Fjeld Halvorsen	1954	1959	1988	Norwegian philologist	1922-2013
1922	Gunnar von Proschwitz	1954	1958	1988	Swedish Romance philologist	1922-2005
1922	P. J. Honey	1954		1985	Irish-Vietnamese language scholar and historian	1922-2005
1922	Joel Veinberg	1954	1954	1983	Latvian orientalist and historian of Jewish origin	1922-2011
1922	Annemarie Schimmel	1954	1954	1992	German Orientalist and scholar who wrote extensively on Islam and Sufism	1922-2003
1922	Micaela Portilla	1954	1954	1989 w	Spanish anthropologist	1922-2005
1922	Marc-Adélar Tremblay	1954	1954	1984	Canadian anthropologist	1922-2014
1922	Kathrine S. French	1955	1955	1981 w	American anthropologist (ceremonialism and naming practices on the Warm Springs Indian Reservation in the state of Oregon)	1922-2006
1922	Walter Hinck	1956	1956	1987	German Germanist and writer	1922-2015

1922	Hans Frei	1956	1956	1988	German-American biblical scholar and theologian who is best known for work on biblical hermeneutics	1922-1988
1922	Harold P. Stern	1957	1960	1977	American art historian and curator specializing in Asian art	1922-1977
1922	Платон Олександрович Білецький	1957		1998	Ukrainian painter and art critic, educator	1922-1998
1922	Sol Worth	1957		1977	American painter, photography and visual communication scholar	1922-1977
1922	Denise Bernot	1958	No	1989	w French academic, professor of Burmese	1922-2016
1922	Barbara Harrisson	1958	No	1987	w German-British art historian who also contributed scientifically to nature conservation, primatology, anthropology, and archaeology	1922-2015
1922	Richard Harrison Robbins	1958	1958	1990	American anthropologist, educator, sociologist, author	1922-2010
1922	Ilse Lehiste	1959	1959	1987	w American (Estonian) linguist (phonetics, Estonian language, Serbo-Croatian, phonology)	1922-2010
1922	Louis-Vincent Thomas	1959		1994	French sociologist, anthropologist, ethnologist, and scholar whose specialty was Africa	1922-1994
1922	Hugh Lloyd-Jones	1960		1989	British classical scholar and Regius Professor of Greek at Oxford	1922-2009
1922	Fayek Matta Ishak	1962	1962	1987	Egyptian-Canadian coptologist, author and scholar	1922-2006
1922	Francis Bessac	1963	1963	1991	American anthropologist	1922-2010
1922	Haim Zafrani	1964	1969	1991	French-Moroccan Native scholar and writer	1922-2004
1922	Alma Sabatin	1965		1979	Italian essayist, linguist, teacher and feminist activist	1922-1988
1922	Lesley Gill	1976	1984	1987	w American author (political violence, gender, free market reforms and human rights in Latin America, especially Bolivia) and a professor of anthropology at Vanderbilt University	
1923	Sebastiano Timpanaro	1943		1983	Italian Italian classical philologist, essayist, literary critic and committed Marxist	1923-2000
1923	Walter Jens	1944	1944	1997	German philologist, literature historian, critic, university professor and writer	1923-2013
1923	Robert Ludwig Kahn	1945	1950	1970	German Jewish-American scholar of German studies and poet	1923-1970
1923	Walter Belardi	1946	1946	1987	Italian glottologist and linguist	1923-2008
1923	Riccardo Picchio	1946	1946	1993	Italian philologist (Italian and Slavic Studies)	1923-2011

1923	Myra L. Uhlfelder	1946	1952	1991 w	American professor of classics at Bryn Mawr	1923-2011
1923	Eric Robert Wolf	1947	1951	1992	Austrian anthropologist (studies of peasants, Latin America, advocacy of Marxist perspectives within anthropology)	1923-1999
1923	René de Nebesky-Wojkowitz	1947	1949	1959	Czech ethnologist and Tibetologist	1923-1959
1923	Anthony F.C. Wallace	1947	1950	1988	Canadian-American anthropologist (Native American cultures, especially the Iroquois)	1923-2015
1923	Cheikh Anta Diop	1948	1959	1986	Senegalese historian, anthropologist, physicist, and politician who studied the human race's origins and pre-colonial African culture	1923-1986
1923	Johann Karl Werner Winter	1949	1949	2010	German Indo-European specialist and linguist	1923-2010
1923	William A. Smalley	1949	1956	1987	American linguist (development of the Romanized Popular Alphabet for the Hmong language)	1923-1997
1923	Leonard Boyle	1949	1949	1997	Irish-Canadian scholar in medieval studies and palaeography and was the first Irish and North American Prefect of the Vatican Library	1923-1999
1923	Robert H. Brower	1950	1952	1988	American professor of Far East Language and Literature, Japanese Language and Literature, chair of Far East Language and Literature	1923-1988
1923	Hugh Kenner	1950	1950	1999	Canadian literary scholar, critic and professor	1923-2003
1923	Harry Oster	1950	1953	1993	American folklorist and musicologist	1923-2001
1923	Alan P. Merriam	1950	1951	1980	American cultural anthropologist and ethnomusicologist	1923-1980
1923	Robert Austerlitz	1951	1955	1992	Romanian-American linguist	1923-1994
1923	Jalāl Āl-e-Ahmad	1951	1951	1969	Iranian prominent Iranian novelist, short-story writer, translator, philosopher, socio-political critic, sociologist as well as an anthropologist	1923-1969
1923	Morris Halle	1951	1955	1996	Latvian-American linguist	1923-2018
1923	Morton Fried	1951	1951	1986	American distinguished Professor of Anthropology	1923-1986
1923	Charles Miller Leslie	1951	1959	1991	American medical anthropologist, who was an avid contributor of published works in his branch of anthropology	1923-2009

1923 Eric Wolf	1951	1951	1992	Austrian-American anthropologist, best known for his studies of peasants, Latin America, and his advocacy of Marxist perspectives within anthropology	1923-1999
1923 Murray Krieger	1952	1952	1994	American literary critic and theorist	1923-2000
1923 Muharrem Ergin	1952		1990	Turkish linguist and Turkologist	1923-1995
1923 Bojan Čop	1952	1971	1990	Slovenian linguist	1923-1994
1923 Peter Avery	1952		1990	British eminent scholar of Persian and a Fellow of King's College, Cambridge	1923-2008
1923 Koentjaraningrat	1952	1952	1988	Indonesian anthropologist, "the father of Indonesian anthropology "	1923-1999
1923 Thomas Barthel	1952	1952	1988	German ethnologist and epigrapher who is best known for cataloguing the undeciphered rongorongo script of Easter Island	1923-1997
1923 David Shepherd Nivison	1953	1953	1988	American Sinologist and scholar (late imperial and ancient Chinese history, philology, and philosophy)	1923-2014
1923 Rodney Needham	1953	1953	1990	British social anthropologist	1923-2006
1923 Doireann MacDermott	1954	1964	2001 w	Irish translator, writer, an academic in the field of Spanish philology	
1923 Арутюнова Нина Давыдовна	1954	1954	2018 w	Russian linguist	1923-2018
1923 Sebastiano Timpanaro	1955	No	1983	Italian classical philologist, essayist, and literary critic, marxist	1923-2000
1923 Earl Wilson Stevick	1955	1955	1984	American expert in language learning and teaching	1923-2013
1923 Henry George Fischer	1955	1955	1992	American Egyptologist and poet	1923-2005
1923 André Caquot	1952		1994	French orientalist, specialized in semitic history and civilisations and professor of Hebrew and Aramaic language at the Collège de France	1923-2004
1923 Paul Gerhard Klussmann	1955	1955	1988	German Germanist, educator	1923-2019
1923 Zbigniew Gołąb	1958	1958	1993	Polish-American linguist and Slavist	1923-1994
1923 Devendra Varma	1958		1991	Indian-American expert on Gothic literature	1923-1994
1923 John W. McCoubrey	1958	1958	1995	American art historian	1923-2010
1923 Israel Yeivin	1959	1968	1990	Israeli linguist, scholar of Masorah and the Hebrew language	1923-2008
1923 Jonas Zemvaldas Balkevičius	1963	1963	2000	Lithuanian linguist, Doctor of Humanities	1923-2000

1923	Victoria Alexandra Fromkin	1964	1965	1992	American linguist	1923-2000
1923	Keith Baird	1964	1964	1998	Barbados-American educator and linguist (linguistic anthropology and the politics of language is considered trailblazing)	1923-2017
1923	Jean Bollack	1964	1964	1992	French philosopher, philologist and literary critic	1923-2012
1923	Beatrice Medicine	1969	1983	1989 w	American Native scholar, anthropologist, and educator known for her work in the fields of Indigenous languages, cultures, and history	1923-2005
1924	Georges Poisson	1945		1992	French art historian	
1924	Marijan Mole	1946	1949	1963	Slovenian-Polish scholar of Middle and Modern Iranian studies, who also contributed to the fields of Islamic and particularly Sufi studies.	1924-1963
1924	Gilbert Ouy	1946		1985	French historian, palaeographer and librarian	1924-2011
1924	Ladislav Zgusta	1947	1949	2007	Czech–American historical linguist and lexicographer	1924-2007
1924	Göran Malmqvist	1947		1990	Swedish linguist, literary historian, sinologist and translator	1924-2019
1924	Miroslav Komárek	1948	1949	2005	Czech historical linguist (Czech language, morphology, phonology)	1924-2013
1924	Arthur Danto	1949		1992	American art critic, philosopher, and professor	1924-2013
1924	Siegfried Lienhard	1949	1949	1995	Swedish professor of Indology at Stockholm University and a scholar of Sanskrit and the Newar language	1924-2011
1924	Elizabeth Lyding Will	1949	1949	1989 w	American Classical archaeologist and a leading expert on Roman amphorae	1924-2009
1924	Pavle Ivić	1950	1954	1975	Serbian South Slavic dialectologist and phonologist	1924-1999
1924	Samuel E.Martin	1950	1950	1994	American professor of Far Eastern Languages at Yale University and the author (on the Korean and Japanese languages)	1924-2009
1924	Jan Pouwer	1950	1955	1987	Dutch anthropologist with a thorough grounding in his profession in terms of fieldwork and theory	1924-2010
1924	Antoine Culioli	1951	1960	1992	French linguist of Corsican origins (author of linguistic theory known as “Théorie des Opérations Énonciatives”)	1924-2018
1924	Roy Andrew Miller	1951	1953	1999	American linguist (Tibetan language, Japanese language)	1924-2014

1924	Munro S. Edmonson	1951	1952	1994	American linguist and anthropologist (Mesoamerican languages and Mesoamerican cultural heritage)	1924-2002
1924	Lyll Powers	1951	1955	1992	Canadian professor of English	1924-2018
1924	Fuat Sezgin	1951	1951	2010	Turkish orientalist of Kurdish origin who specialized in the history of Arabic-Islamic science	1924-2018
1924	Anna Sadurska	1951		1984 w	Polish Classical philologist and epigrapher	1924-2004
1924	Erika Bourguignon	1951	1951	1990 w	Austrian-American anthropologist known primarily for her work on possession trance and other altered states of consciousness	1924-2015
1924	Richard Newbold Adams	1951	1951	1990	American anthropologist	1924-2018
1924	Nancy Oestreich Lurie	1952	1952	1994 w	American anthropologist (North American Indian history and culture)	1924-2017
1924	Joey Lee Dillard	1952	1972	1999	American linguist (African American Vernacular English)	1924-2009
1924	Šimon Ondruš	1952	1952	1990	Slovak linguist, Slavist and indo-Europeanist, member of several international linguistic societies	1924-2011
1924	H. Brett Melendy	1952	1952	1993	American prominent historian, writer, researcher, publisher, autobiographer, dean, history professor, and filipinologist	1924-2008
1924	Lisa Peattie	1952	1968	1984 w	American Professor Emerita of Urban Anthropology	1924-2018
1924	John Leslie Melville Trim	1953		1997	British linguist	1924-2013
1924	Géza Vermes	1953	1953	1991	British academic, Bible scholar, and Judaist of Hungarian Jewish origin	1924-2013
1924	Colin Turnbull	1954	1964	1983	British-American anthropologist, one of the first anthropologists to work in the field of ethnomusicology, LGBT scientist	1924-1994
1924	Alojz Rebula	1954	1960	2013	Slovene philologist	1924-2018
1924	Edward Wasiolek	1954	1955	1996	American literary scholar	1924-2018
1924	Anthony Kennedy Warder	1954	1954	1990	British Indologist	1924-2013
1924	Carmen Blacker	1954		1996 w	British Japonologist	1924-2009
1924	F. G. Bailey	1954		1989	British social anthropologist	
1924	Harold Barclay	1954	1961	1989	Canadian professor emeritus in anthropology	1924-2017
1924	Edward Bruner	1954	1954	1989	American anthropologist known for his contributions to the anthropology of tourism, particularly his constructivist, processual approach that centers on experience and narrative in and beyond tourist settings	

1924	Robert F. Murphy	1954	1954	1990	American anthropologist (studies of the Mundurucu (Mundurucu) people of the Amazon and the Tuareg people of the Sahara)	1924-1990
1924	William Arrowsmith	1954	1954	1992	American classicist, academic, and translator	1924-1992
1924	Hans-Günther Thalheim	1954	1954	1989	German professor of German language and linguistics and of Literary sciences	1924-2018
1924	Mervyn Meggitt	1955	1963	1993	Australian anthropologist, one of the pioneering researchers of highland Papua New Guinea and of Indigenous Australian cultures	1924-2004
1924	Neville Chittick	1955		1983	British scholar and archaeologist	1924-1984
1924	Erica Reiner	1955	1955	1996 w	American Assyriologist and author	1924-2005
1924	Chia-ying Yeh	1955		1989	Chinese-Canadian scholar of classical Chinese poetry	
1924	Rusiate Nayacakalou	1955	1963	1972	Fijian social anthropologist	1927-1972
1924	McKim Marriott	1955	1955	1998	American musicologist known for his studies of Japanese traditional music	
1924	Manning Nash	1955	1955	1994	American anthropologist and ethnographer	1924-2001
1924	David Marshall Lang	1955		1991	British Professor of Caucasian Studies	1924-1991
1924	James M. Robinson	1955	1955	1999	American scholar who retired as Professor Emeritus of Religion	1924-2016
1924	Jacques Bompaire	1956	1956	1996	French Hellenist and scholar of ancient Greek and Greek literature of the Roman and Byzantine period	1924-2009
1924	Paul Garelli	1956	1963	1986	French Assyriologist	1924-2006
1924	Elizabeth Spillius	1956	1956	1999 w	Canadian-English anthropologist, sociologist, and Kleinian psychoanalyst	1924-2016
1924	Otto Kaiser	1956	1956	1993	German Old Testament scholar	1924-2017
1924	Sally Falk Moore	1957	1957	1989 w	American legal anthropologist	
1924	June Helm	1958	1958	1999 w	American anthropologist, primarily known for her work with the Dene people in the Mackenzie River drainage	1924-2004
1924	Mary B. Moser	1959	No	1999 w	American field linguist and Bible translator who worked on behalf of the Seri people of Mexico	1924-2013
1924	Barbara Hardy	1959	No	1989 w	British literary scholar, author, and poet	1924-2016
1924	John M. Rosenfield	1959	1959	2001	American art historian, with a specialization in Japanese art	1924-2013
1924	Åke W. Sjöberg	1960	1960	1996	Swedish Assyriologist, specialized in Sumerian language and literature	1924-2014

1924	Tseng Yu-ho	1960	1972	1986	Chinese-American artist, art historian and educator	1924-2017
1924	Aris Poulianos	1960	1961	1987	Greek anthropologist and archaeologist	
1924	Ernest Becker	1960	1960	1974	American cultural anthropologist and author of the 1974 Pulitzer Prize-winning book, <i>The Denial of Death</i>	1924-1974
1924	Charles Dowsett	1960	1961	1991	British the first Calouste Gulbenkian Professor of Armenian at the University of Oxford	1924-1998
1924	Desmond C. Derbyshire	1961		1998	British linguist who specialized in Carib languages	1924-2007
1924	Сергій Іванович Дорошенко	1962		2018	Ukrainian linguist	1924-2018
1924	Lucien Stryk	1963		1991	American poet, translator of Buddhist literature and Zen poetry, and former English professor	1924-2013
1924	Lola Romanucci-Ross	1963	1963	1989 w	American cultural anthropologist who has authored and co-authored a number of works on medical, social, and cultural anthropology, with fieldwork in Melanesia (Manus), rural Mexico, and her mother's home town in Italy	1924-2017
1924	William Vaios Spanos	1964	1964	2010	American the Heideggerian literary critic	1924-2017
1924	Margaret Hubbard	1970		1986 w	Australian-British classical scholar (philology)	
1924	Robert I. Levy	1971	1971	1991	American psychiatrist and anthropologist known for his fieldwork in Tahiti and Nepal and on the cross-cultural study of emotions	
1924	Mamlakat Nakhangova	1971	1971	1990 w	Tajikistani philologist, Indologist, and Orientalist	